

authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p., tlc and ir spectra).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Professor S. C. Bhattacharyya, Director and Professor A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, for their interest in the work. They are indebted to Dr. D. B. Deb, Deputy Director, Botanical Survey of India, Howrah and Dr. N. C. Nair, Deputy Director, Botanical Survey of India, Southern Circle, Coimbatore for the plant material. They are also grateful to Professor R. D. H. Murray of the University of Glasgow, Glasgow, U. K., for kindly supplying the authentic samples of the coumarins reported in this paper.

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Chemical Examination of Three Indigenous Plants

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Manuscript received 22 April 1981, accepted 10 December 1981

CANTHIUM *didymum* Roxb.¹ (Syn. *C. dicoccum* Gaertn.) (Rubiaceae) is a low branched evergreen tree distributed in many parts of India. A survey of literature revealed that no chemical work has been done on the leaf of this plant though the bark has been examined by different workers²⁻⁵.

Air dried powdered leaves (460 g) collected from Mayurbhanj Dist., Orissa were exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit. The alcoholic extract was divided into ether soluble and ether insoluble parts. Ether soluble part was separated into acid and neutral fractions by extraction with aqueous NaOH (10%). Chromatography of the acid fraction over silica gel yielded two pure compounds A and B. Compound-A (21 mg) was crystallised from CHCl₃-pet. ether; m.p. 145-146°. It showed bright blue fluorescence in uv light and gave positive test for coumarin. UV (EtOH): 227, 251, 296, 346; ir: 1710, 1600 cm⁻¹. It was identified as aesculetin dimethyl ether by comparison with an authentic sample (m. m. p., tlc, superimposable ir).

Compound-B was crystallised from CHCl₃-pet. ether, (6 mg); m. p. 203-204°. It responded to colour test for coumarin and showed blue fluorescence in uv light. UV (EtOH): 229, 252, 299, 344. It was identified as scopoletin by comparison with authentic compound (m. m. p., tlc).

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over alumina. Pet. ether-benzene (7:3) eluted fraction (40 mg) furnished fine needles (ethanol); m. p. 209-10°, [α]_D⁺²¹ (CHCl₃). The compound gave positive Liebermann-Buchard test and TNM colour reaction for an unsaturated triterpene. It exhibited no characteristic uv absorption above 220 nm and showed ir peaks at 3600, 1368, 1365, 875 cm⁻¹. It gave an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°) crystallised in needles (CHCl₃-pet. ether); m. p. 216-217°, [α]_D⁺⁴⁸ (CHCl₃). It was identified as lupeol by comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir).

The pet. ether-benzene (1:9) eluates afforded fine flakes (19 mg); m. p. 136-137°. It gave pink-violet-blue-green colour with L-B reagent and yielded an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°); m.p. 127-128°, identical (m. m. p., tlc, ir) with an authentic specimen of β -sitosterol acetate.

Pithecellobium saman Benth. (Syn. *Samanea saman* Merrill.) (Mimosaceae) is a large tree popularly known as raintree. The bark and leaves of this plant have been examined chemically⁶⁻⁹. The pods were reported¹⁰⁻¹² to contain lupeol, α -spinasterol, α -spinasterol- β -D-glucoside, palmitic acid, stearic acid, acacic acid and mixtures of flavonoids. Our re-investigation of the pods resulted in the isolation of echinocystic acid and acacic acid lactone not reported earlier along with lupeol and α -spinasterol.

The air-dried powdered pods (6.8 g) of *P. saman* collected locally was Soxhleted with alcohol for 62 hr. The ether insoluble part of this alcoholic extract was hydrolysed with 3% alcoholic H₂SO₄ and worked up in the usual manner. The sapogenins thus obtained were separated into acid and neutral fractions.

The neutral part, on repeated chromatography over alumina, yielded acacic acid lactone (20 mg) crystallised from ethanol as needles; m.p. 253-255°, ir: 3400, 1760, 1371, 970 cm⁻¹. It gave an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°) crystallised as colourless small needles; m. p. 233-235°. The identity of the compound was established by direct comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir). The acid fraction was esterified and chromatographed over alumina. Benzene-CHCl₃ (1:1) eluted a pure compound crystallised from ethanol; m. p. 210-211°, ir: 3500, 1700, 1370 cm⁻¹. It afforded an acetate (Ac₂O-py, 100°); m. p. 200-203°. Finally, the methyl ester and its acetate was identified as methyl echinocystate and diacetate methyl echinocystate by comparison with authentic specimen (m. m. p., tlc, ir).

The ether soluble part, on chromatography over alumina, yielded lupeol; m.p. 209-210°; ir: 3400, 1639, 882 cm⁻¹, acetate m.p. 211-212°, identified as

lupeol by direct comparison with authentic compound (m. m. p., tlc, ir); α -spinasterol; m. p. 164-166°, acetate m. p. 179-180°, the identity was confirmed through m. m. p., tlc and superimposable ir with an authentic material.

Solanum nigrum L. (Solanaceae) is a commonly occurring herbaceous weed. The tetraploid variety of this species bears orange coloured fruits. Presence of carotenoid in these fruits was reported earlier¹⁴. We have characterised the fruit carotenoid as α -carotene.

Fresh orange coloured berries (50 g) of *S. nigrum* collected locally were ground into a paste with sand and extracted with alcohol at room temperature. The alcoholic extract was shaken with pet. ether several times. The combined pet. ether portions was diluted with ether and to this 30% methanolic KOH was added and kept at room temp in a dark place for 17 hr. The ether layer separated, washed, dried and slowly concentrated. The reddish yellow coloured residue obtained responded to colour reaction for carotenoid. It gave a single spot on thin layer chromatogram. Absorption spectra of material isolated quickly from chromatoplates were recorded in three different solvents, *n*-hexane: 421, 444, 473; CS₂: 475, 510; CHCl₃: 454, 484. It was identified as α -carotene by comparison of the spectral data with that reported for α -carotene¹⁵.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. K. Jain, Director, Botanical Survey of India, Howrah-3 for facilities. They are also indebted to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-32 for rotation and ir spectra, to Prof. A. K. Barua, Bose Institute, Calcutta-9 for authentic samples of scopoletin and aesculetin dimethyl ether and to Dr. Nilima Banerji, Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-32 for authentic sample of α -spinasterol.

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Biologically Active New 1-Substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazoles

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Manuscript received 17 July 1981, accepted 6 November 1981

A number of compounds having various substituents at 1, 2 and 5 positions of imidazole ring have been synthesised and tested for various therapeutic effects¹⁻³. 1-Aryl substitution in imidazole ring^{4,5} enhances the microbial activity. The divalent sulphur containing molecules such as 'NCS' have also been found to possess good antimicrobial properties^{6,7}. Recently, 1-aryl-2-mercaptobenzoyl imidazoles⁸ were found to have good amoebicidal and fungicidal properties.

Considering the above facts, we have synthesised some new 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazoles and screened them for amoebicidal and fungicidal activity *in vitro*.

Experimental

Synthesis of 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazole: Equimolecular quantities of 1-substituted-2-mercapto-4-phenylimidazole⁹ and benzoyl chloride and sodium carbonate (0.015 mole) in DMF were refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. Later on, the reaction mixture was worked up to get a solid 1-substituted-2-mercaptobenzoyl-4-phenylimidazole. The compounds thus prepared were characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectroscopy. The following characteristic frequencies were obtained for them:

IR KBr: $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹): 1660 (C=O; C₆H₅-COSR type), 1600 (C=N), 1590, 1490, 1460, 1440 (characteristic for five membered heteroaromatics), 1010-1240 (CH in-plane) and 600, 700 (CH out-of-plane).

Pharmacological screening:

Determination of amoebicidal activity¹⁰ against Schizopyrenus russelli in vitro: The amoebae, *S. russelli*, were grown in monobacterial culture of non-nutrient agar plates (2.5% w/v agar; 0.5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichia coli* (2-3 days old grown on nutrient agar slages as food). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep

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